

Primality test amateur.

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Abstract

The test consists in comparing a number ($p?$) of which one wants to establish the primality or not, with a composite number (which I call (L)) which contains the majority of possible prime numbers; it does not recognize prime numbers but composite numbers.

This is obviously a test limited to the prime numbers present in (L) .

In this review [v2] I highlight a further possibility that the test offers, it is a rough factoring that seems to me interesting for the speed of execution

This article is written in English and Italian, the original language is Italian which is my language, the translation into English was done using the Google translator.

The test consists in comparing a number ($p?$) with (L) ; does not recognize prime numbers but composite numbers.

$(p?)$ represents the number to be tested.

(L) is the product of a series of consecutive prime numbers from 2 to (p_n) .

I have been advised that what I call (L) is commonly referred to as "primorial"; I have my reasons for considering (L) something more than the simple product of consecutive prime numbers starting from 2 up to (p_n) .

The use I make of (L) in this test is actually simply linked to the presence in (L) of all the prime factors from 2 to (p_n) , so "primorial" may be suitable in this case.

Before writing this article, I ran an internet search to see if the idea of using "primorials" in a primality test had already been used.

I have found that the APR primality test (by Aldeman-Pomerance-Rumely) also uses "primorials", but I couldn't find a description of the test that I can understand; in particular on the use of "primorials".

What I found on the APR primality test is that it is based on three fundamental elements:

- Cyclotomic Field Theory.
- The "primorial" numbers.
- The Chinese Rest Theorem (CRT).

In the amateur test that I propose I only use the "primorial" and I do it in a banal way even if effective even if limited, so I think it is something else.

I describe it with some simple examples.

The test consists in dividing the number to be tested using as a divisor a "primorial" with a value as large as possible, obviously (L) can be broken down into various parts.

If the result of the calculation produces a reduced fraction of the calculated one, it means that in $(p?)$ there is at least one of the prime factors present in (L) , therefore $(p?)$ is composite.

If the calculation produces a fraction identical to the one calculated, it means that none of the prime factors present in (L) are present in $(p?)$; so it is possible that $(p?)$ is a prime number.

With a second calculation, it is possible to identify any prime factors in common; since the prime factors present in (L) are all in quantity 1, the calculation does not provide any indication on the quantity.

In the following examples I first perform the calculation $p?/L$ and then the calculation $L/D(p?/L)$ where $D(p?/L)$ indicates the denominator of the reduced fraction obtained with the calculation $p?/L$.

$L_1(2 \div 5003) = 662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669$
5162308171904959433252543520942821138593836613046401796730863128212912845258435337008607191976899
8276210589668133798843699373532614609017602228200286157656436994518475265956834307170066146463014
1486533957460457974452694591694521699138645304032272388119927057705852884069592045682375777934200
5172327325962454569651405997973316048694543031765294519902852797928015442418638015945385345642602
8005624739396559879416799984287684212909533379197581253747445927459068219850636423046316411218470
9731157949004892807849440989321077602212503686476874832550988910977437131218599155982041293156005
1002432882438974629037830799761240684539739060633472215021032241156198428895560707759275533236870
6951022329514298568055222319470273549894939513524749846999755754432425816537111068579367313478992
7747524224437238091404536985575126673600102010262443449834729869985622639921533280980238386476121
8856648895833955912628008090535111674660153435247393383794412612111502824696027018310038026269227
8014680047991623376890544298481260186335628179472940148893887403921757168383007170932468693686307
4981285494701302197347660312378395654439762866528495744673174275241088989781844863433627777183877
0225186156927544261792042230025698178572998054458713744875288562452766178093753428850014750489093
3551578016518267929807614013521539564282875158312137209424212028773025191054628460536858168605421
6971731742726852554594763241827842827510575550245308564587207400362720309752197486955150604387685
4342504525786067368124227622458543591676450953692228034472957766856673675079268462857095475680400
5921290336318395922395514960083209385860573327479770850667200763162385444227704150061018005868349
2272154713859757014034830113973359549936468204055349822683382921232566186725643616948909288709939
2156043018588464380179339148008941453976782412513849179699546660554957694749856267062776884361123
1070227481326821927920988024556065459232266426112360841647268017819718519482557759856298634236423
7859948157265719087512750345794070300902931540712868627573164421360258907233113904654060791096676
4832356162090

$L_2(5009 \div 10007) = 89811984097462122683835258707473343631483166359577913907882097513805111007673309320$
3100464024720664786544654094675173064269485171048594667518633233028254484090255316897012176498419
6098504996194201431481537193835499058859376931421937068283576046246354946380642181776412565140918
8244079895828111415093586665686779932983084395277315934790208949968089593231784993058941784105153
2661256224658067098849074527418794571203202970907561544178879880583261039014457725999782988390879
195744127448620600034474663148410830450962607345219279380006174457910695352731371243330103322090
5021544371728669794604729564705416608895377703171380502200801676631144923525669233815710354963114
6991608400799027416609216395222827172217079356824864884972907373200159190939822128260523765828253
6969667235979471593464943153257411391253803665862177147535697404401032679981491625442911159313249
8118809503180816465078656750178470443963467750644714211245737120855955524834132656019354503373018
492478801697844757929706324367635550789230295074039310684057543428438927214204294428339134052895
4759370410728049547590168108171328161731416809856031236481009829517532950925693115885021133999885
5204712728599837201047965565662803014326394931467118711800248294915740455362235077448167361330025
7511830262958500465350589033610363924847263423039803980846373371385965823022089510093908686354169
0691150410271929786235764658514510328037322256155810427359098029949332955924692001712415473415428
0870309991234232307990167008081082716255152784545014091575453140858988859620984655411138546350265
8210433213063516085221410441037267495356932765321773486542933024709272912697742501899176557775753
7138711912303882551867491097314198266879902951706377642553572096124826134134557788381360023108798
1612908799208005764429661913236245728136557806934459766331148733785706874786547289869894528815526
3922474519179829548055108702118826159392227899610874025908439906742099860591979405023378503815232
6618020860475491982096840370567200643765261422832581560519714563568234487368366400235159784992254
0018013532794836065784362011039195305607737553922206007066761452014925392374020748194459193188268
099409318988267158606868198502693564234104833

$p? = 1234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234$
5678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901
2345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678
9012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345
6789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012
3456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
012345678901234567891

For the calculation I use PARI / GP; it is important that the result is fractional.

8282536969667235979471593464943153257411391253803665862177147535697404401032679981491625442911159
313249811880950318081646507865675017847044396346775064471421124573712085595524834132656019354503
373018492478801697844757929706324367635550789230295074039310684057543428438927214204294428339134
0528954759370410728049547590168108171328161731416809856031236481009829517532950925693115885021133
9998855204712728599837201047965565662803014326394931467118711800248294915740455362235077448167361
3300257511830262958500465350589033610363924847263423039803980846373371385965823022089510093908686
3541690691150410271929786235764658514510328037322256155810427359098029949332955924692001712415473
4154280870309991234232307990167008081082716255152784545014091575453140858988859620984655411138546
3502658210433213063516085221410441037267495356932765321773486542933024709272912697742501899176557
7757537138711912303882551867491097314198266879902951706377642553572096124826134134557788381360023
1087981612908799208005764429661913236245728136557806934459766331148733785706874786547289869894528
8155263922474519179829548055108702118826159392227899610874025908439906742099860591979405023378503
8152326618020860475491982096840370567200643765261422832581560519714563568234487368366400235159784
9922540018013532794836065784362011039195305607737553922206007066761452014925392374020748194459193
188268099409318988267158606868198502693564234104833

The result is an identical fraction to the calculated one, so in this case there are no prime factors in common.
Now I can see what are the prime factors in common between (p?) and (L₁).

$L_1/D(p?/L_1)=662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669$
5162308171904959433252543520942821138593836613046401796730863128212912845258435337008607191976899
8276210589668133798843699373532614609017602228200286157656436994518475265956834307170066146463014
1486533957460457974452694591694521699138645304032272388119927057705852884069592045682375777934200
5172327325962454569651405997973316048694543031765294519902852797928015442418638015945385345642602
8005624739396559879416799984287684212909533379197581253747445927459068219850636423046316411218470
9731157949004892807849440989321077602212503686476874832550988910977437131218599155982041293156005
100243288243897462903783079976124068453973906063347221502103224115619842889560707759275533236870
6951022329514298568055222319470273549894939513524749846999755754432425816537111068579367313478992
7747524224437238091404536985575126673600102010262443449834729869985622639921533280980238386476121
8856648895833955912628008090535111674660153435247393383794412612111502824696027018310038026269227
8014680047991623376890544298481260186335628179472940148893887403921757168383007170932468693686307
4981285494701302197347660312378395654439762866528495744673174275241088989781844863433627777183877
0225186156927544261792042230025698178572998054458713744875288562452766178093753428850014750489093
3551578016518267929807614013521539564282875158312137209424212028773025191054628460536858168605421
697173174272685255459476324182784282751057550245308564587207400362720309752197486955150604387685
4342504525786067368124227622458543591676450953692228034472957766856673675079268462857095475680400
5921290336318395922395514960083209385860573327479770850667200763162385444227704150061018005868349
2272154713859757014034830113973359549936468204055349822683382921232566186725643616948909288709939
2156043018588464380179339148008941453976782412513849179699546660554957694749856267062776884361123
1070227481326821927920988024556065459232266426112360841647268017819718519482557759856298634236423
7859948157265719087512750345794070300902931540712868627573164421360258907233113904654060791096676
4832356162090/14103297952124447004237290864213704458636122731016320021455565996838445095425616847
1844577921450466062966664947734488145130608379502405242591419805598472615166920392241212949089190
9978686727884886556038273270199436864140617395792089367790588434829670605856722485836322767364818
3620031628382073626765413887118972223865939120112851750476342977171440550061363182809482603739956
0468195155900552392650418115021233474809546692404931176479146869208466553520051460383317986922247
7149532034568923331061264187233708248600274670922961650664973349913350192940847885881341410987472
7334249599105297976442720200872113214417068351142265465421969169976829307173004651045871958325386
2979808562401754020736788038953186409376266802958736882387553638983854387200614799163994878202834
8270360660049564134012086281325946176032976488074755845741425526718179413315245470448267646113052
744527122391966887740620009653160798141858723621298430730744329212489331119998330495340005072052
6834443758487145403317289957618947555567545960711388242412421157715151308570738213340815107192048
2814425844256340247305891288176563431067794375067648360428699869944764292705710276748317712099865
6661169814584993644727603141708774008418179569422692095654141982431388108276378337124753906973982
6356813301833126117963016851962340972301671765916052313058401601884307505663363696881464893930861
4700713863362053580168719310936457905097112401599113024195945196000612192025341587839585890599332
030248876024984525218201265453706016686867043777664793799246536327667291921484089308233088310731
6528815797968633746114215409098350181778546307467099834639031339526954397312235729116231002031397
4553317474262474859487710542871491132114592778155903824911716323420492816711579312854256617404380

1776431322440720420362000741066254752330849712089447986166440071977047501408228205183339338495504
4667918213681246563071918709343574658328808016647074762748504245673628828887122337367384314401794
9175129153776198443019742999745203320541685792902683241720035048255698291883393245909784176566685
8813571488258665228065691760645655192985125594288100273800586663072794899125685810934141575761512
6952443241620470
=47

The result is a prime number, so 47 is the only prime factor of (p?) less than 10007.

I want to conclude with a verification, I do it by constructing a composite number in which there are prime factors present both in L_1 and in L_2 in varying quantities.

$p? = 2^2 * 2^3 * 5^7 * 7^11 * 13^29 * 29^67 * 67^307 * 313^313 * 313^313 * 2393^2393 * 4021^4021 * 4021^5711 * 5711^5711 * 6563^6563 * 6899^6899 * 7499^7499 * 8297^8297 * 9791^9791 * 9781^9781 * 9781^10007 * 10007^10007$
=462743524879700766144725725380265182853825669300519135320887853844828781803932895095339012411842
354228720826330772440

$p?/L_1 = 462743524879700766144725725380265182853825669300519135320887853844828781803932895095339012411842354228720826330772440 / 662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669516230817190495943325254352094282113859383661304640179673086312821291284525843537008607191976899827621058966813379884369937353261460901760222820028615765643699451847526595683430717006614646301414865339574604579744526945916945216991386453040322723881199270577058528840695920456823757779342005172327325962454569651405997973316048694543031765294519902852797928015442418638015945385345642602800562473939655987941679998428768421290953337919758125374744592745906821985063642304631641121847097311579490048928078494409893210776022125036864768748325509889109774371312185991559820412931560051002432882438974629037830799761240684539739060633472215021032241156198428895560707759275533236870695102232951429856805522231947027354989493951352474984699975575443242581653711106857936731347899277475242244372380914045369855751266736001020102624434498347298699856226399215332809802383864761218856648895833955912628008090535111674660153435247393383794412612111502824696027018310038026269227801468004799162337689054429848126018633562817947294014889388740392175716838300717093246869368630749812854947013021973476603123783956544397628665284957446731742752410889897818448634336277771838770225186156927544261792042230025698178572998054458713744875288562452766178093753428850014750489093355157801651826792980761401352153956428287515831213720942421202877302519105462846053685816860542169717317427268525545947632418278428275105755502453085645872074003627203097521974869551506043876854342504525786067368124227622458543591676450953692228034472957766856673675079268462857095475680400592129033631839592239551496008320938586057332747977085066720076316238544422770415006101800586834922721547138597570140348301139733595499364682040553498226833829212325661867256436169489092887099392156043018588464380179339148008941453976782412513849179699546660554957694749856267062776884361123107022748132682192792098802455606545923226642611236084164726801781971851948255775985629863423642378599481572657190875127503457940703009029315407128686275731644213602589072331139046540607910966764832356162090$
=8577342119817310188236141975040675867062389278853447543003618196287255699389127325441517996077332/122865774177462706678408063899079810997835296365265486198048309348533605011433767856910881149950681834481906759371781842968396134070415100967236641845317956398177329062443563480025730287450320722150644402817139843776550963877376168350088049146549688473342329373378413966874039981724311889883617469226688757951880966763900666081512516998080414230056155477144818433213776067543081456140468994953937661912457810488441911667085984223534328987721036961583150032906837268852234574413702181942488322874445616219822530612951749673526000246232115629387823735299986665841958459411512780230229815721404393842495380148209631300165122277132563762155813073985936635938235017521881551246465617030365411244683235078226938248154124212304322905294232127580998328974053848357021626799532562360356757487802957521773669411456146029602824455965139701597701269254931923731302796694058250313122749551166024297036661362373217096632363543425610699870062424011869448204270445674983852795617873284002867606537194385034203241007317876246718165815964925648093324037353257822551210912940971009265905483384379929284080793115365525906425158889155034980500480997882419599627270613605734977242246289967581756226693768083701333579690589905393609525139822732696509708770856739536571705194111241586611007569270983948744910032827718682022470902583426221009469302110265893155285190743716260985360934448600998668321798244384331567700132733511918901521775993170420617632453312143239518315026101233769923801268014902726862952875596877881326117310483339018290209632047255614472007339237174176645938794533239620004123486184209728042382247465863052634768060435056168356976674253251755610977811

8051406989143628005807362523644984806223195262754515590907023949178917468137489250650523114873525
4023217594021955227760091433926832991123592107020099649149233278134281155312383443768797871937612
6626135739903466381307448532945609856309441078023475262612591540056582637730884107644761979943515
3798376997331171824766958467387044702023629789124914610065151484796868328322438845911934421574011
73247971727484411410583579573712159720717285364037181118182344472469556887214685227

$p?/L_2=4627435248797007661447257253802651828538256693005191353208878538448287818039328950953390124$
 $11842354228720826330772440/8981198409746212268383525870747334363148316635957791390788209751380511$
1007673309320310046402472066478654465409467517306426948517104859466751863323302825448409025531689
7012176498419609850499619420143148153719383549905885937693142193706828357604624635494638064218177
6412565140918824407989582811141509358666568677993298308439527731593479020894996808959323178499305
8941784105153266125622465806709884907452741879457120320297090756154417887988058326103901445772599
978298839087919574412744862060003447466314841083045096260734521927938000617445791069535273137124
3330103322090502154437172866979460472956470541660889537770317138050220080167663114492352566923381
5710354963114699160840079902741660921639522282717221707935682486488497290737320015919093982212826
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801821359031793849031689660202963328773009
=15418401914368924628844431111537

$\text{factor}(15418401914368924628844431111537)=[5711\ 1][6563\ 1][6899\ 1][7499\ 1][8297\ 1][9781\ 1][9791\ 1][10007\ 1]$

In the end I also got a start of factoring; in any case it is a test limited to the maximum prime factor contained in (L_1) or in L_2 or ..., which in this case is 10007.

As an amateur test I don't mind, waiting for something better (from my part); I'd like to know how the APR primality test uses "primorials".

This is the link that corresponds to this article.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5062840>

These two links correspond to two of my other articles on prime numbers published on zenodo.org, the first I titled "The mechanism of prime numbers" and the second "Finding prime numbers".

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769674>

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4786547>

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Test di primalità amatoriale.

Dante Servi

Abstract

Il test consiste nel mettere a confronto un numero ($p?$) del quale si vuole stabilire la primalità o meno, con un numero composto (che io chiamo (L)) il quale contiene la maggior parte di numeri primi possibili; non riconosce i numeri primi ma i numeri composti.

Si tratta evidentemente di un test limitato ai numeri primi presenti in (L) .

In questa revisione [v2] evidenzio una possibilità ulteriore che il test offre, si tratta di un abbozzo di fattorizzazione che mi sembra interessante per la velocità di esecuzione.

Questo articolo è scritto in Inglese ed Italiano, la lingua originale è l'Italiano che è la mia lingua, la traduzione in Inglese è stata fatta utilizzando il traduttore di Google.

Il test consiste nel mettere a confronto un numero ($p?$) con (L) ; non riconosce i numeri primi ma i numeri composti.

$(p?)$ rappresenta il numero da testare.

(L) è il prodotto di una serie di numeri primi consecutivi da 2 fino a (p_n) .

Sono stato messo al corrente che quello che io chiamo (L) è comunemente definito "primoriale"; ho le mie ragioni per considerare (L) qualcosa di più che il semplice prodotto dei numeri primi consecutivi partendo da 2 fino a (p_n) .

L'utilizzo che in questo test faccio di (L) è in realtà semplicemente legato alla presenza in (L) di tutti i fattori primi da 2 a (p_n) , quindi "primoriale" può essere in questo caso adatto.

Prima di scrivere questo articolo ho eseguito una ricerca su internet per verificare se fosse già stata utilizzata l'idea di utilizzare i "primoriali" in un test di primalità.

Ho scoperto che il test di primalità APR (di Aldeman-Pomerance-Rumely) utilizza anche i "primoriali", ma non sono riuscito a trovare una descrizione del test che io possa capire; in particolare sull'utilizzo dei "primoriali".

Quello che ho trovato sul test di primalità APR è che si basa su tre elementi fondamentali:

- Teoria dei campi ciclotomici.
- I numeri "primoriali".
- Il teorema del Resto Cinese (CRT).

Nel test amatoriale che propongo utilizzo soltanto i "primoriali" e lo faccio in un modo banale anche se efficace seppur limitato, penso quindi che si tratti di altro.

Lo descrivo con alcuni semplici esempi.

Il test consiste nel dividere il numero da testare utilizzando come divisore un "primoriale" di valore il più grande possibile, ovviamente si può scomporre (L) in varie parti.

Se il risultato del calcolo produce una frazione ridotta di quella calcolata significa che in $(p?)$ è presente almeno uno dei fattori primi presenti in (L) , quindi $(p?)$ è composto.

Se il calcolo produce una frazione identica a quella calcolata, significa che in $(p?)$ non è presente nessuno dei fattori primi presenti in (L) ; quindi è possibile che $(p?)$ sia un numero primo.

Con un secondo calcolo, è possibile individuare gli eventuali fattori primi in comune; essendo i fattori primi presenti in (L) tutti in quantità 1, il calcolo non fornisce nessuna indicazione sulla quantità.

Negli esempi che seguono eseguo prima il calcolo $p?/L$ e successivamente il calcolo $L/D(p?/L)$ dove $D(p?/L)$ indica il denominatore della frazione ridotta ottenuta con il calcolo $p?/L$.

$L_1(2 \div 5003) = 662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669$
5162308171904959433252543520942821138593836613046401796730863128212912845258435337008607191976899
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4832356162090

$L_2(5009 \div 10007) = 89811984097462122683835258707473343631483166359577913907882097513805111007673309320$
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8118809503180816465078656750178470443963467750644714211245737120855955524834132656019354503373018
492478801697844757929706324367635550789230295074039310684057543428438927214204294428339134052895
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5204712728599837201047965565662803014326394931467118711800248294915740455362235077448167361330025
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7138711912303882551867491097314198266879902951706377642553572096124826134134557788381360023108798
1612908799208005764429661913236245728136557806934459766331148733785706874786547289869894528815526
3922474519179829548055108702118826159392227899610874025908439906742099860591979405023378503815232
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099409318988267158606868198502693564234104833

$p? = 1234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234$
5678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901
2345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678
9012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345
6789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012
3456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789012345678901234567890123456789
012345678901234567891

Per i calcoli utilizzo PARI/GP; è importante che il risultato sia frazionario.

8282536969667235979471593464943153257411391253803665862177147535697404401032679981491625442911159
313249811880950318081646507865675017847044396346775064471421124573712085595524834132656019354503
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188268099409318988267158606868198502693564234104833

Il risultato è una frazione identica a quella calcolata, quindi in questo caso non ci sono fattori primi in comune.
Ora posso vedere quali sono i fattori primi in comune tra (p?) ed (L₁).

$L_1/D(p?/L_1)=662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669$
5162308171904959433252543520942821138593836613046401796730863128212912845258435337008607191976899
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6951022329514298568055222319470273549894939513524749846999755754432425816537111068579367313478992
7747524224437238091404536985575126673600102010262443449834729869985622639921533280980238386476121
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0225186156927544261792042230025698178572998054458713744875288562452766178093753428850014750489093
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697173174272685255459476324182784282751057550245308564587207400362720309752197486955150604387685
4342504525786067368124227622458543591676450953692228034472957766856673675079268462857095475680400
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1844577921450466062966664947734488145130608379502405242591419805598472615166920392241212949089190
9978686727884886556038273270199436864140617395792089367790588434829670605856722485836322767364818
3620031628382073626765413887118972223865939120112851750476342977171440550061363182809482603739956
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7149532034568923331061264187233708248600274670922961650664973349913350192940847885881341410987472
7334249599105297976442720200872113214417068351142265465421969169976829307173004651045871958325386
2979808562401754020736788038953186409376266802958736882387553638983854387200614799163994878202834
8270360660049564134012086281325946176032976488074755845741425526718179413315245470448267646113052
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6834443758487145403317289957618947555567545960711388242412421157715151308570738213340815107192048
2814425844256340247305891288176563431067794375067648360428699869944764292705710276748317712099865
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4553317474262474859487710542871491132114592778155903824911716323420492816711579312854256617404380

1776431322440720420362000741066254752330849712089447986166440071977047501408228205183339338495504
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9175129153776198443019742999745203320541685792902683241720035048255698291883393245909784176566685
8813571488258665228065691760645655192985125594288100273800586663072794899125685810934141575761512
6952443241620470
=47

Il risultato è un numero primo, quindi 47 è l'unico fattore primo di (p?) inferiore a 10007.

Voglio concludere con una una verifica, lo faccio costruendo un numero composto nel quale ci siano fattori primi presenti sia in L₁ che in L₂ in quantità varia.

$p? = 2 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 5 \cdot 7 \cdot 7 \cdot 11 \cdot 13 \cdot 29 \cdot 29 \cdot 67 \cdot 67 \cdot 307 \cdot 313 \cdot 313 \cdot 313 \cdot 313 \cdot 2393 \cdot 2393 \cdot 4021 \cdot 4021 \cdot 4021 \cdot 5711 \cdot 5711 \cdot 5711 \cdot 6563 \cdot 6563 \cdot 6899 \cdot 6899 \cdot 7499 \cdot 7499 \cdot 8297 \cdot 8297 \cdot 9791 \cdot 9791 \cdot 9781 \cdot 9781 \cdot 9781 \cdot 10007 \cdot 10007 \cdot 10007$
=462743524879700766144725725380265182853825669300519135320887853844828781803932895095339012411842
354228720826330772440

$p?/L_1 = 462743524879700766144725725380265182853825669300519135320887853844828781803932895095339012411842354228720826330772440/66285500374984900919915267061804410955589776835776704100841160185140691948500399181766951623081719049594332525435209428211385938366130464017967308631282129128452584353700860719197689982762105896681337988436993735326146090176022282002861576564369945184752659568343071700661464630141486533957460457974452694591694521699138645304032272388119927057705852884069592045682375777934200517232732596245456965140599797331604869454303176529451990285279792801544241863801594538534564260280056247393965987941679998428768421290953337919758125374744592745906821985063642304631641121847097311579490048928078494409893210776022125036864768748325509889109774371312185991559820412931560051002432882438974629037830799761240684539739060633472215021032241156198428895560707759275533236870695102232951429856805522231947027354989493951352474984699975575443242581653711106857936731347899277475242244372380914045369855751266736001020102624434498347298699856226399215332809802383864761218856648895833955912628008090535111674660153435247393383794412612111502824696027018310038026269227801468004799162337689054429848126018633562817947294014889388740392175716838300717093246869368630749812854947013021973476603123783956544397628665284957446731742752410889897818448634336277771838770225186156927544261792042230025698178572998054458713744875288562452766178093753428850014750489093355157801651826792980761401352153956428287515831213720942421202877302519105462846053685816860542169717317427268525545947632418278428275105755502453085645872074003627203097521974869551506043876854342504525786067368124227622458543591676450953692228034472957766856673675079268462857095475680400592129033631839592239551496008320938586057332747977085066720076316238544422770415006101800586834922721547138597570140348301139733595499364682040553498226833829212325661867256436169489092887099392156043018588464380179339148008941453976782412513849179699546660554957694749856267062776884361123107022748132682192792098802455606545923226642611236084164726801781971851948255775985629863423642378599481572657190875127503457940703009029315407128686275731644213602589072331139046540607910966764832356162090$
=8577342119817310188236141975040675867062389278853447543003618196287255699389127325441517996077332/122865774177462706678408063899079810997835296365265486198048309348533605011433767856910881149950681834481906759371781842968396134070415100967236641845317956398177329062443563480025730287450320722150644402817139843776550963877376168350088049146549688473342329373378413966874039981724311889883617469226688757951880966763900666081512516998080414230056155477144818433213776067543081456140468994953937661912457810488441911667085984223534328987721036961583150032906837268852234574413702181942488322874445616219822530612951749673526000246232115629387823735299986665841958459411512780230229815721404393842495380148209631300165122277132563762155813073985936635938235017521881551246465617030365411244683235078226938248154124212304322905294232127580998328974053848357021626799532562360356757487802957521773669411456146029602824455965139701597701269254931923731302796694058250313122749551166024297036661362373217096632363543425610699870062424011869448204270445674983852795617873284002867606537194385034203241007317876246718165815964925648093324037353257822551210912940971009265905483384379929284080793115365525906425158889155034980500480997882419599627270613605734977242246289967581756226693768083701333579690589905393609525139822732696509708770856739536571705194111241586611007569270983948744910032827718682022470902583426221009469302110265893155285190743716260985360934448600998668321798244384331567700132733511918901521775993170420617632453312143239518315026101233769923801268014902726862952875596877881326117310483339018290209632047255614472007339237174176645938794533239620004123486184209728042382247465863052634768060435056168356976674253251755610977811

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$p?/L_2=$ 4627435248797007661447257253802651828538256693005191353208878538448287818039328950953390124
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= $30012418112440991200112358865262014965387252877068759673747018489035360327815896524120/582498657$
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$L_1/D(p?/L_1)=$ 662855003749849009199152670618044109555897768357767041008411601851406919485003991817669
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Alla fine ho ottenuto anche un inizio di fattorizzazione; si tratta comunque di un test limitato al massimo fattore primo contenuto in (L1) oppure in L2 oppure ..., che è in questo caso è 10007.

Come test amatoriale non mi dispiace, in attesa di qualcosa di meglio (da parte mia); non posso fare a meno di chiedermi in che modo il test di primalità APR utilizza i "primoriali".

Questo è il link che corrisponde a questo articolo.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5062840>

Questi due link corrispondono a due miei altri articoli sui numeri primi pubblicati su zenodo.org, il primo lo ho intitolato "The mechanism of prime numbers" ed il secondo "Finding prime numbers".

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769674>

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4786547>

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